

Is *Xylella fastidiosa* really emerging in France?

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Listed as a quarantine pest worldwide except in the Americas, *Xylella fastidiosa* was first detected in Europe very recently with reports from Italy in 2013, France in 2015, Germany and Spain in 2016. A large genetic diversity has been evidenced in these different outbreaks, with representatives from at least the three main subspecies (*i.e.* *fastidiosa*, *multiplex*, and *pauca*). In France, most foci are consecutive to *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* ST6 and ST7. However, foci of *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* ST53 *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa/sandyi* ST76 and *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* ST79 have been detected. Molecular dating of phylogenetic trees exploiting genome data provided dates of divergence between French isolates and their American relatives that can be considered as proxy or lower bounds of introduction dates. According to these analyses, *X. fastidiosa* may have been introduced in France as early as 1965 (ST7) and 1980 (ST6). These dates are also coherent with increases in introduction of alien plant material in Corsica. Altogether these results and the various detections of foci of genetically diverse *X. fastidiosa* strains in Europe support the idea that *X. fastidiosa* has been introduced in Europe in separate occasions since ~50 years with apparent diverse epidemiological patterns and socio-economic consequences.